

HUMAN RIGHTS IN INDIA AND ITS COMPARATIVE EFFECT AND EXAMINATION ON INTERNATIONAL CONTEXT

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Abstract

Human Rights fundamentally presupposes that all humans are born with equal dignity and rights. These are moral demands that are repugnant and inherent in all humans just because they are members of humanity. Today, these claims are defined and formalized, and subsequently referred to as human rights. All humans are born free, with equal dignity and rights. But man has made him unequal in many ways. Some were given special treatment, while others were not, and dealing with the worldwide situation would be the most difficult issue. Oppression and slavery were present. They are created and deconstructed in the furnace of experience and the irreversible process of human fight for freedom. All human rights are based on the principle of equal dignity for all individuals. These rights have been identified as universal in application and leaving norms, inalienable in exercise, and inherent in all individuals. Humans are entitled to some basic and inherent rights; otherwise, their lives would be pointless. These rights have been violated in bits and pieces for decades, creating the most contentious marginal variables to discuss and having a direct influence on the global scale. Humanitarian groups, notably the United Nations High Commissioner for Human Rights, have recently scrutinized India's human rights record. How other countries shape our perceptions of modern India. This study paper broadens the scope of the reason and prompts us to consider what we have lost in dignity and how others see us in general.

Meaning of Human Rights:

The phrase "right" refers to a multidimensional dynamic notion that encompasses nearly all aspects of life, including social, cultural, economic, and political domains. Prof. H.J. Laski defines rights as "social conditions without which no man can be his best self." Prof. Green defines a right as "a power claimed and recognized as contributing to the

common good." Human rights are classified as fundamental rights, basic rights, inherent rights, natural rights, and birth rights. Human rights are extraordinary rights that every individual is entitled to just because they are human. These rights are important to guarantee every person's dignity as a human being, regardless of race, religion, language, caste, gender, or any other factor. Human rights are based on the principle of human equality.

Human rights are universal, indisputable, and subjective. Human rights are universal, which means they apply to all of us, regardless of ethnicity, color, gender, sexual orientation, age, religion, political beliefs, or kind of government. They are undeniable, which implies they are absolute and intrinsic. Human rights are subjective in the sense that they are the attributes of particular people who have them due to their rationality, agency, and autonomy. The concept of universality has been challenged for ignoring cultural diversity. When human rights are guaranteed by a written constitution, they are referred to as basic rights since the written constitution is the state's primary legislation.

Scholarly Definitions on Human Rights:

According to the United Nations Centre for Human Rights, human rights are "those rights which are inherent in our nature and without which we cannot live as human beings" Human rights are defined as "rights derived from the inherent dignity of human person" in the Universal Declaration of Human Rights, which was adopted on December 10, 1948. The Protection of Human Rights Act, 1993, states: "Human Right means rights relating to life liberty, equality and dignity of the individuals guaranteed by the constitution or embodied in the International Covenants and enforceable by courts in India."

D.D. Basu described human rights as "the essential rights that every person should possess against the state or any public authority simply by being part of the human family, regardless of any other factors." He also asserts that the idea of human rights is as ancient as the old principle of natural rights based on natural law, while the term human is relatively new. Dr. Upendra Baxi, in his effort to define human rights, notes that for the first time in contemporary history, we are transitioning from viewing rights as tools for individuals opposing state authority to perceiving human rights also as rights pertaining to humanity. M.C. Bhandal reflects that the desire for safeguarding human rights arose from the widespread violence that occurred during the two World Wars of the century.

Justice M.H. Beg, former Chief Justice of India, while defining human rights stated that human rights imply justice, equality and freedom from arbitrary and discriminatory treatment; these cannot be subjected to coercion for holding particular religious beliefs.

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P.P.Rao defines Human rights as the inherent dignity and inalienable rights of all members of human family, recognizing them as their foundation of freedom, justice and peace in the world.

Justice Nagendra Singh opined that respect for the human personality and its absolute worth, regardless of colour, sex, race is the very foundation of human rights. These rights are essential for the adequate development of the human personality and for human happiness and progress. According to S. Kim, human rights are "claims and demands essential to the protection of human life and the enhancement of human dignity, and should therefore enjoy full social and political sanctions". Subhash C Kashyap opined that human rights are those "fundamental rights to which every man inhabiting any part of the world should be deemed entitled by virtue of having been born a human being". Milne defined "human rights are simply what every human being owes to every other human being and as such represent universal moral obligation". According to Nickel, human rights are norms which are definite, high priority universal and existing and valid independently of recognition or implementation in the customs or legal system of particular countries.

Justice RanganathMisra, the first chairman of the National Human Rights Commission of India, has observed that "it is an obligation which all of us have to perform. Man, wherever he lives, whatever religion he professes, whatever food he takes, is a member of one family. All of us must learn to live like a member of one family. The whole world is one family. We will be able to develop the culture of human rights. In the absence of Human Rights, individuals and families are disintegrating in the modern era. It is a challenge to human progress. We should all be prepared and united to face the challenge of the indiscipline. Everyone must realize the what is prescribed by law is not for next man, or the man to follow, but for you".

Development of Human Rights:

The human rights which we are enjoying today is developed and meta morphed though varies stages. The important benchmarks in the development of human rights are the following gazetted documents and struggles of approvals:

- a) Magna Carta of 1215
- b) Influence of Social Contract Theory
- c) English Bill of Rights of 1689
- d) American Declaration of Independence of 1776
- e) American Bill of Rights of 1791

- f) French Declaration of the Rights of Man of 1789
- g) The Bolshevik Revolution of Russia of 1917
- h) Universal Declaration of Human Rights of 1948
- i) International Covenants on Human rights.

Each of these declarations and the movement referred above, have made important contributions in advancing the concept of human rights. However, being product of their own time and specific circumstances, they lack totality of concept and were narrow in their scope and application. For instance, in the Greek political system, rights existed only for the 'citizens' and not for the majority who were referred to as "aliens" and "slaves". Magna Carta yielded certain concessions only for the feudal lords (not for common man), though it set limitation to arbitrary rule and laid the foundation for the rule of law. The American Declaration followed by constitutional amendments or Bill of Rights contain fairly exhaustive guarantees for the rights of man. But in practice their application was largely confined to those who constituted what was abbreviated as WASP (white, Anglo-Saxon, and protestant). Slavery continued to be a part of the system; the blacks of African origin were referred to as "Negro" not as man. It was in 1864 that slavery in America was legally abolished after a bitter civil war which threatened the unity of the United States. While American and the French Declarations set the seal on the basic principles of freedom of thought, human dignity and democratic government, the countries undergoing rapid industrialization have experienced the need for more social justice and economic security. The Bolshevik Revolution in Russia (1917) went a step further. It emphasized that economic and social rights were as important as the civil and political rights.

Adoption of Universal Declaration of Human Rights:

The Universal Declaration of Human Rights (UDHR) was adopted by the General Assembly of the United Nations on 10th December 1948. The declaration is not a legally binding document; it is an ideal for all mankind. In the words of Eleanor Roosevelt, it proclaims "a common standard of achievement for all people and all nations". In its final form, it comprises of a list of civil, political, economic, social and cultural rights to which all persons are entitled. Universal Declaration is a declaration of principles directed to the peoples of the world. This has been considered as one of the greatest achievements of the UN. It has been maintained that "the Universal Declaration of Human Rights has had a significant influence on the development of standards that states are not only respected but also have legal commitment to be respected".

International Covenants on Human Rights:

To meet the demand for a legally binding document for the protection of the human rights, two international covenants were approved by the General Assembly on 16th December 1966. These are: -

1. International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights,
2. International Covenant on Economic Social and Cultural Rights.

What is more important about the two UN covenants is that they contain “International mechanism” to monitor and oversee that the obligation of human rights are observed by states parties to the covenants. Two supervisory bodies – that Human Right Committee under ICCPR and committee on Economic, social and cultural Rights under ICESER consisting of 18 human rights experts are created to help States Parties to the covenants in fulfilling these obligations.

Optional Protocol There are two Optional Protocols to the International Covenant on Civil and Political Rights. The two international covenants together with the universal declaration and the optional protocols comprise the international bill of rights.

Benevolent Approaches to The Study of Human Rights:

Approaches are the method for analysing the concept. Approaches are the analyses of any idea or social phenomena by the use of a particular theory or intellectual principles. Historical background, social cultural conditions, social and economic system, ideology, government and its relations to the people all these considerably influenced in the origin and development of the human rights. There are mainly three approaches to the study of human rights. They are:

1. Western or Liberal approach.
2. Marxian or Socialist approach.
3. Third World approach.

Western or Liberal Approach:

The Western approach is also known as the liberal democratic approach. It is based on the idea of liberalism which defends the principles of competitive individualism, private property, and market ethics. It cherishes the individual liberty, development and human progress through the functioning of the above principles. The liberal approach is based on the natural law and natural rights view of human rights. The advocates of liberal approach agree with the Locke’s understanding on the natural rights of life, liberty and property. They argue

the duty of the government is just to maintain law and order so that everybody will get a chance to enjoy their rights. Liberal approach prefers a minimum or night watchman state.

Thomas Hobbes, John Locke, J.S, Mill were the ardent advocates of the liberal approach. The main principles of the liberal approach are the personal liberty, private property, open market, open competition; It laid emphasis for the creation of a good society and state based on personal liberty.

Marxian or Socialist Approach:

The Marxist approach of the human rights can be seen in the writings of Karl Marx, the Engels and Lenin. The Marxian approach gives more importance to the social rights than the individual rights. It states that the personality development is possible only through the society. Therefore, more importance should be given to the social rights rather than the individual rights. Therefore, the duty of the state is to guarantee the civil and economic rights to its citizens. According to Marx personal rights and personal liberty makes a man more selfish and exclude him from the society. Therefore, social rights should be given priority.

The developing and underdeveloped nations believe in the Marxian approach to the human rights. According to Marx natural rights are not seen in history therefore they are the creation of the human mind. The natural right theory is made for the protection of the interest of the bourgeoisie. Marx state that man is a social animal and therefore they should utilize their abilities qualities and work for the society. To achieve the social good the people should do their duties and responsibility to the society. At the same time, it is the duty of the state to provide social welfare and development to the people. Marx maintained that inequality existing in the society due to the existence of the classes. In a capitalist society, there is no equal enjoyment of rights. The capitalist will enjoy all the rights and majority working class is deprived of the rights and they are exploited. Therefore, only in a classless society the people can enjoy the rights in its full meaning.

Third World Approach:

The approach of the Third World countries on human rights was not very different from the western concept. But since most of the Afro-Asian, Latin American countries were under colonial rule there were human rights violations in that part of the world. The nationalist movements in all these countries were for the protection of their basic rights. Among the Third World countries, India was the pioneer in the formulation of the concept of the human rights. In India a large section of people such as Harijans, Girijans and landless

labours have not only suffered economic exploitation but have been subjected to allsorts of exploitation.

In the Third World, the perspective applied to each concept and reality of human rights varied with prevailing social philosophy, culture, ideology and historical tradition. Understandably in the case of former colonies the emphasis will lie as much on civil and political rights and the third-generation rights, with a somewhat decisive inclination in favor of community interest, where in the context of community interest, where social and economic progress and development are regarded as of primary importance. Human Rights violation is a common feature in most of the third world countries. The criminalization of politics and lack of accountability has become common in these countries. The brutalization of state power is reflected in the form of state repression. Judiciary, press, human rights activists and non-governmental organization etc. gives some relief to the people. There is an extremely close nexus between human rights and peace, freedom national self-determination economic cultural and technological development. Third world approach theory believes in the *Human Rights Trade Off theory* and gives primary to economic development over human rights. The theory stands to postpone human rights for the sake of development. The slogan of the third word is that “development first and rights second”. The argument is that human rights can be realized in the long run, if we dedicate the short run to development. So, the states are blind towards the grave human rights violation persuaded in the name of development. The negative response of the Indian state towards the Narmada Bachavo Andolon, a movement for protecting the rights of the marginalized who are the victims of the development project is an example to shoe the third world’s approach to human rights.

Concluding Remarks on Research Findings:

In this research article I have been referring the journey of Human Rights from post independent to present situation we travelled with treaded marks. Let me take opportunity to brief how current scenario is creating barrier to developed and under developing countries. On June 14 the OHCHR released its report referring to Kashmir issue and highlighting the various cases of extreme human right violations. The report was harshly criticized by the Indian Ministry of external affairs despite substantial evidence of violation against the people of Kashmir. India said the report was literally biased and disrespectful of its sovereignty. But the UN report was an unprejudiced attempt to save human lives. Over all debatable issue is report is not biased but shows that violations originating from India in Kashmir have become more frequent. India’s response to the report is unacceptable when human life is at stake.

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Instead it should welcome the suggestions made by UN. It is unwise for New Delhi to stand by while its security forces shot Kashmir citizens with pellet guns.

Some sections of the report in web repositories indicating vigilante violence aimed at religious minorities, marginalize communities and critics of the government. The government failed to promptly or credibly investigate the attacks. Dissent was labeled anti-national, and activist, journalists and academics were targeted for their views, chiding free expression. The despicable ideology of considering oneself superior to other leads ultimately to suffering for innocent humans regardless of their origin. It appears that this ideology has taken root in India in the form of discrimination against minorities. In one of the leading daily reported that Muslims, continued through the year amid rumors that they sold, bought or killed cows for beef. Instead of taking prompt legal action against the attackers, police filed complaints against the victims under laws of banning cow slaughter. As of November 2017, there had been 38 such attacks, and 10 people killed during the year.

HRW's world report 2018 also states that in India. Multiple high-profile cases of rape across the country during the year once again exposed the failures of the criminal justice system. Nearly five years after the government amended laws and put in place new guidelines and policies aimed at justice for survivors of rape and sexual violence, girls and women continue to face barriers to reporting such crimes, including humiliation at police stations and hospitals. Such traumatic experiences require urgent attention and victims need to be provided with health care, social protection and therapy for post traumatic stress disorder. Resources must be used to improve the criminal justice, safety, security and social protection and law enforcement in order protect the human life.

The entire world must help humanitarian organisations impress upon India the importance of human rights. The world must help India understand that being spiteful and dismissing criticism is not a solution. Instead, it must focus on human right violations. India achieve this but it requires a push in the right direction from other countries to improve human rights on the subcontinent. I request at last with humble let's join hands to protect the human rights bring laurels to our nation.

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